

Diagnostic Accuracy of RPR and TPHA Tests for Syphilis in Pregnant Women: A Study on Biological False Positives and Screening EfficacyShazia Umar¹, Archana Kumari Sharma², Rajkumar Gurjar³, Rambabu Sharma⁴¹Post Graduate, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, PIMS, Udaipur²Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, PIMS, Udaipur³Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, PIMS, Udaipur⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Microbiology, PIMS, Udaipur

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Abstract

Background: Syphilis, caused by *Treponema pallidum*, remains a significant public health issue, particularly for pregnant women, with the potential to cause severe maternal and fetal complications, including stillbirth, preterm birth, low birth weight, and congenital syphilis. Early diagnosis and treatment are essential to prevent these adverse outcomes.

Objective: This study aimed to assess the diagnostic accuracy of Rapid Plasma Reagin (RPR) and *Treponema Pallidum* Hemagglutination Assay (TPHA) tests in identifying syphilis in pregnant women and to evaluate the prevalence of biological false-positive results.

Materials and Methods: A retrospective descriptive study was conducted from November 2023 to November 2024, involving 6,363 non-duplicate venous blood samples collected from antenatal care patients at PIMS Hospital. All samples were initially tested with the RPR test, and reactive cases were further tested using the TPHA. Data were analyzed using MedCalci software, with statistical significance set at a p-value of < 0.05.

Results: Out of 6,363 samples, 109 (1.71%) were RPR reactive. These samples underwent semi-quantitative RPR testing at dilutions of 1:2, 1:4, 1:8, 1:16, 1:32, and 1:64. Higher dilutions (1:8 and above) showed a higher number of TPHA-positive cases, with 46 cases at dilutions >1:16. A total of 39 biological false-positive cases (0.61%) were identified in dilutions below 1:8. Among the 109 RPR reactive cases, the majority (73.39%) were in the 21-30 years age group, with 25.69% of false positives also occurring in this group. However, this age distribution was not statistically significant.

Conclusion: Syphilis diagnosis in pregnancy requires a combination of RPR and TPHA tests to minimize false-positive results. Regular screening and early treatment are crucial to prevent syphilis-related complications. The study underscores the need for confirmatory testing in clinical practice to ensure accurate diagnosis and effective treatment, ultimately reducing maternal and neonatal morbidity and mortality associated with syphilis.

Keywords: Syphilis, RPR, TPHA, biological false positives, antenatal screening, pregnancy, *Treponema pallidum*.

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Introduction

Syphilis, a sexually transmitted infection caused by the bacterium *Treponema pallidum*, remains a significant public health concern worldwide, particularly for pregnant women. When a pregnant woman is infected, syphilis can have severe consequences for both the mother and the foetus. The potential outcomes for the infant include stillbirth, neonatal death, prematurity, low birth weight, and congenital syphilis, a condition that can result in long-term neurological, ocular, or auditory impairments if left untreated.[1]

Syphilis is a major cause of stillbirth in areas where screening and treatment are inadequate. According to a study by Sharma et al [2]., the prevalence of stillbirth due to syphilis in India remains

alarmingly high, with untreated syphilis accounting for a significant proportion of neonatal mortality. A study conducted by Kalawat et al [3]., found that pregnant women with untreated syphilis had a higher rate of preterm deliveries and babies with low birth weight compared to those who were screened and treated during pregnancy.

Neonates born to mothers with untreated syphilis are at risk for congenital syphilis, which can manifest with a range of severe symptoms. These include skin rashes, hepatosplenomegaly, anemia, and neurological issues such as hydrocephalus, seizures, and developmental delays. A study by Sood et al., in North India highlighted that congenital syphilis is often diagnosed late, leading

to irreversible damage to the infant's organs, particularly the eyes, ears, and brain.[4]

Children born with congenital syphilis who survive may experience long-term consequences, including hearing loss, vision problems, and cognitive impairments. The work by Deka et al., in India showed that a significant proportion of children with congenital syphilis required long-term medical and developmental interventions, highlighting the need for early screening and treatment.[5]

While the fetus is at high risk, syphilis also presents serious health risks to the pregnant woman, particularly when the infection remains undiagnosed and untreated. Syphilis lesions increase the susceptibility of pregnant women to other sexually transmitted infections (STIs), including HIV. A study by Arora et al., in India found a higher co-infection rate of syphilis and HIV among pregnant women, suggesting the synergistic effect of these infections.[6] In a cohort study by Ghosh et al., 10% of pregnant women with untreated syphilis experienced spontaneous abortion, emphasizing the impact of syphilis on pregnancy outcomes.[7] Syphilis can lead to placental insufficiency, where the placenta fails to supply the foetus with adequate nutrients and oxygen. This can result in intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) and preterm birth. A study by Rao et al., found that syphilis was significantly associated with placental pathology, highlighting its potential to disrupt the normal function of the placenta.[8] In untreated cases, syphilis can lead to chronic pelvic inflammatory disease (PID), which may increase the risk of ectopic pregnancy and infertility. Although less common in pregnant women, PID remains a significant complication in cases of untreated syphilis.

Despite the availability of diagnostic tools, syphilis is often underdiagnosed during pregnancy, primarily due to the lack of visible symptoms in many infected individuals. This underscores the necessity of regular screening, especially in areas with high syphilis prevalence or among populations at increased risk. The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) and the World Health Organization (WHO) recommend routine syphilis screening during early prenatal care visits, with retesting in the third trimester and at delivery for high-risk women. [9,10]

Accurate diagnosis is essential not only for effective treatment but also for preventing the transmission of syphilis to the new-born, which can be eliminated with proper antenatal care. The ability to diagnose syphilis relies on a combination of clinical evaluation, serological testing, and sometimes molecular diagnostics, ensuring that appropriate treatment can be initiated swiftly. Given the far-reaching effects of untreated syphilis

in pregnancy, this article highlights the importance of early and accurate diagnosis in preventing maternal and neonatal morbidity and mortality associated with syphilis.

Materials and Methods

This study was designed as a descriptive retrospective study, conducted from November 2023 to November 2024. The confidentiality of all data was strictly maintained. All samples were initially tested using the Rapid Plasma Reagin (RPR) test. All RPR reactive samples were then further tested using the TPHA test. All tests were performed in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions, using commercially available kits.

Inclusion Criteria: A total of 6,363 non-duplicate venous blood samples were collected from antenatal care patients attending the outpatient department (OPD) and those admitted to the wards and labour room at PIMS Hospital. All samples were collected under aseptic precautions and transported to the microbiology laboratory. A standard proforma was used to gather the medical and demographic data of the patients.

Exclusion Criteria: Samples with insufficient volume, hyperlipidemic samples, and repeated samples from the same patients were excluded from this study.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was performed using MedCalci software, and a p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Out of 6363 patient samples, only 109 showed reactivity to the RPR test. These reactive samples were then subjected to quantitative RPR testing at various dilutions, with the following results: 1:2, 1:4, 1:8, 1:16, 1:32, and 1:64. We have a dataset in Table 1 showing RPR dilution levels, the number of RPR reactive cases, and their outcomes in terms of TPHA positivity and TPHA negativity. Dilutions of RPR above 1:16 showed a higher number of TPHA-positive cases (n=46). At the 1:8 dilutions, 22 patients tested TPHA positive, while 9 patients were TPHA negative. Additionally, 39 biological false positive cases were observed in dilutions below 1:8 on the semi-quantitative RPR test. No TPHA-positive cases were detected in dilutions below 1:8. Biological false positive results accounted for 0.61% (39 out of 6363 samples). Among the 109 RPR reactive cases, 80 (73.39%) were in the 21-30 year's age group. Additionally, 28 (25.69%) of the false positive cases were also in the same age group (Table 2). However, this difference is statistically not significant, indicating that false positive cases can occur across all age groups.

Table 1: RPR and TPHA tests results in suspected syphilis cases

Semi-quantitative RPR dilution	RPR reactive cases, (%)	TPHA positive cases, (%)	TPHA negative cases, (%)
1:2	2 (1.83)	0 (0)	2 (5.13)
1:4	30 (27.52)	2 (2.86)	28 (71.80)
1:8	31 (28.44)	22 (31.42)	9 (23.07)
1:16	22 (20.18)	22 (31.42)	0 (0)
1:32	21 (19.26)	21 (30)	0 (0)
1:64	03 (2.77)	3 (4.30)	0 (0)
Total (n=109)	109	70	39

Table 2: Age group wise distribution of semi-quantitative RPR test reactivity

RPR Dilution	21 – 30 years	31 – 40 years	41 – 50 years
1:2	2	0	0
1:4	24	4	2
1:8	22	6	3
1:16	14	4	4
1:32	16	2	3
1:64	2	1	0
Total (n=109)	80	17	12

Discussion

Syphilis can cause serious complications during pregnancy, including spontaneous abortion, stillbirth, non-immune hydrops, intrauterine growth restriction, perinatal death, and severe health issues in liveborn infected infants. Although proper treatment of pregnant women can prevent many of these complications, the main challenge lies in identifying infected women and ensuring they receive treatment. A cost-effective approach involves screening in the first trimester using non-treponemal tests like the Rapid Plasma Reagin (RPR) or Venereal Disease Research Laboratory (VDRL) tests, followed by confirmation with treponemal tests such as TPHA or Fluorescent Treponemal Antibody Absorption (FTA-ABS) assays. High-risk individuals should be retested in the third trimester. Penicillin is the recommended treatment during pregnancy, and the dosage should be determined based on the stage of the maternal infection and the mother's HIV status. Pregnant women who are allergic to penicillin should undergo desensitization before treatment. Even with appropriate treatment, up to 14% of pregnancies may result in fetal death or the birth of an infected infant. Treatment can also be complicated by the Jarisch-Herxheimer reaction, an allergic response to the release of antigens from dying microorganisms, which may cause fetal distress and uterine contractions. Pregnancy does not appear to alter the clinical course of syphilis, but pregnancy-related cervical changes such as hyperemia, eversion, and friability may increase the likelihood of spirochete entry, leading to spirochaetemia. [11] The false

positivity rate for these tests is approximately 1% when used to screen the general population. [12,14]

False reactive results are more commonly observed in certain patient groups, including the elderly, pregnant individuals, and those with drug addiction, malignancies, or autoimmune diseases like systemic lupus erythematosus. Additionally, viral infections such as Epstein-Barr and hepatitis viruses, as well as protozoal or mycoplasma infections, may also contribute to an increased occurrence of false reactive results. [15-16]

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The present study reveals a lower proportion of biological false positives (0.39%), highlighting the importance of TPHA in diagnosing syphilis. If only non-specific, non-treponemal tests had been used, a higher rate of false positives would have been observed (1.71%, or 109 out of 6363 cases). Specific treponemal serological tests detect antibodies against the antigens of the *Treponema* organism itself. However, once positive, these tests have limited utility as they tend to remain positive for life, reflecting either an ongoing or past infection. Therefore, TPHA results cannot be used to assess the success or failure of anti-treponemal therapy. While TPHA is not a 100% sensitive and

specific test, its ease of use in less-equipped laboratories makes it a preferable option compared to more specific treponemal tests, making it more accessible in resource-limited settings. No biological false positive reactions were found in RPR dilutions above 1:8. Therefore, semi-quantitative RPR test results at a dilution of 1:8 or higher can be considered equivalent to TPHA results for syphilis diagnosis, especially in healthcare facilities with limited resources.

Conclusion

A single non-treponemal antibody test, such as RPR, should not be considered conclusive for diagnosing syphilis for several reasons. It only detects reaginic antibodies, which do not necessarily indicate the active stage of the disease. Additionally, biological false positives can occur due to physiological factors or certain acute and chronic infections. Therefore, specific treponemal tests are essential for reducing errors related to the specificity of the method. Our findings suggest that the limitations of screening tests for syphilis diagnosis should not be overlooked, and confirmatory tests like TPHA are necessary. Serology, being crucial for the laboratory diagnosis of syphilis, should always be interpreted in conjunction with the patient's clinical presentation.

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